

WHAT DRIVES CASSAVA FARMERS' OUTPUT MAXIMIZATION POTENTIALS? EMPIRICAL EVIDENCE FROM IMO STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract:

Cassava is one of Nigeria's most strategic food and industrial crops, serving as a major source of dietary energy, rural employment, and raw materials for agro-based industries. Therefore, maximizing cassava output is essential not only for improving household income but also for meeting the growing domestic and international demand for cassava products. However, persistent low productivity and suboptimal resource utilization among cassava farmers continue to undermine the crop's full economic and food security potential. Despite its importance, many cassava farmers operate below optimal production levels due to various socioeconomic and resource-related constraints. Therefore, this study examined the drivers of output maximization among cassava farmers. Specifically, it described the socioeconomic characteristics of farmers, estimated the level of output maximization, and identified constraints limiting optimal production. A multistage and purposive sampling technique was employed to select 192 cassava farmers, particularly members of cassava production groups in key producing communities within the study area. Primary data were collected using a structured questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive statistics and the Cobb–Douglas Production Function (CDPF). The results showed that the mean age of farmers was 43 years, with males constituting 63.02% of the sample. The average farm size was 1.80 hectares (approximately 27 plots), and the mean annual farm income was ₦740,000 (\$546.63). Farmers recorded an average annual cassava output of 20,600 kg. The estimated total elasticity of production was 0.622, indicating decreasing returns to scale and confirming that farmers operated within Stage II of the production function. Although production occurs within the rational stage, resources are not yet optimally utilized, implying potential for increased output. Cassava production remains a critical livelihood activity in the area; however, inadequate production capital (98.96%), limited access to farmland (96.88%), and high labour costs (84.37%) were identified as major constraints to output maximization. The study recommends strengthening cooperative societies to facilitate collective access to productive resources, credit, and inputs. Additionally, given that farmers operate within Stage II of production, targeted government subsidies and improved access to agro-input dealers should be promoted to enhance the use of yield-improving inputs such as improved cassava varieties, fertilizers, and expanded cultivated area.

Keywords: Cassava, Output Maximization, Cobb-Douglas Production Function (CDPF), Constraints, Imo State and Nigeria

1.0 INTRODUCTION

In Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), and particularly across Nigeria, cassava (*Manihot* spp.), is one of the most crucial food security crops for millions of people and has a significant place in the economy [(International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA), 2025; Ofiaju et al., 2025)]. In the second quarter of 2023, cassava contributed 22.35% of Nigeria's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) [(Federal Ministry of Finance (FMF), 2025)]. Cassava has been identified as one of the most important crops for the continent as it contributes significantly to reshaping the livelihoods of rural farmers and positively impacts the economy across SSA (Owoade et al., 2025). It is increasingly clear that cassava is a steady food items in the household diets of most Nigerians (Onubuogu & Esiobu, 2020). According to the Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO) (2025) and Price Waterhouse and Coopers (PwC) (2025), as of 2024, the world cassava production output stood at 303.57 million metric tons (MMT), and the total production output in Africa was 173 million metric tons (MT) (56% of the world production output). During the same period, Nigeria produced 60,001,531 MMT of tuberous roots on 7,737,846 hectares of harvested area. FAO (2025) and PwC (2025), also asserted that Nigeria would need 88.3 million metric tonnes of fresh cassava root planted annually on 9.2 million hectares of land to meet the country's needs, thereby creating a cassava supply gap of nearly 28.3 MMT per annum. This is an indication that there is excess demand cassava tuber in Nigeria. The current cassava production output in Nigeria, as well as the near-zero export of the country's produce, puts Nigeria in an unfavorable position to compete in the implementation of the Africa Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA) [(Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), 2025)]. The inability to satisfy domestic demand and boost production for the local and export markets could be linked to the output maximization and consumption (Olanrewaju, 2025). Cassava supports a growing agro-processing sector, providing raw materials for the production of garri, fufu, starch, flour, ethanol, and animal feed (Oladoyin et al., 2022). Imo State stands out for its favorable agro-ecological conditions that support cassava production (Okenwa-Onuobia et al., 2024). However,, many cassava farmers still operate below optimal output levels due to a range of socioeconomic characteristics (e.g., education, age, and household size), institutional variables (e.g., access to credit, extension services, and market facilities), and agronomic practices (e.g., farm size, use of improved varieties, and fertilizer application) (Esiobu, 2019). The interplay of these factors determines the ability of farmers to achieve optimal output maximization levels. Meanwhile, cassava output maximization refers to the strategic utilization of available land, labour, inputs, and capital resources to achieve the highest possible yield and economic return. It is influenced by both internal (eg., farm management practices, input use, education, access to credit, extension services, and landholding size) and external (such as market access, price volatility, and policy environment) factors (Nwafor, 2020; Esiobu, 2023). Esiobu (2023), noted that while cassava is a resilient crop, its productivity is highly dependent on the intensity and efficiency of resource use. Farmers often face challenges such as limited access to improved cassava varieties, low mechanization, insufficient extension services, poor infrastructure, and inadequate financing (Ikuemonisan et al., 2020; Esiobu,2024; Oniah & Aregbesola, 2025). These constraints directly impact their ability to operate within the production function's economically efficient region. This persistent underperformance raises critical concerns about factors limiting cassava farming efficiency and productivity. Several empirical studies

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(Omoluabi&Ibitoye, 2024; Esiobu et al., 2025; Elenwa et al., 2025), have broadly identified constraints such as poor access to improved inputs, inadequate extension services, climate change, limited capital, and traditional farming practices. However, localized, empirical evidence on the specific determinants that influence output maximization among cassava farmers in Imo State is lacking. Consequently, most agricultural interventions fail to address the root causes of low productivity (Oyotomhe et al., 2025). Moreover, many cassava farmers may be unaware of the optimal stage of the production function in which they operate, which could lead to resource underutilization and poor output maximization (Esiobu, 2019). Without clear insights into the elasticity of key input variables and the returns to scale, farmers and policymakers may be unable to make informed decisions that could drive cassava production, output maximization and productivity gains. Against this background, it became pertinent that the study focused on what determines cassava farmers' maximization potentials, empirical evidence from Imo State, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study were to describe the socio-economic characteristics of cassava farmers, estimate their output maximization potentials, and identify the constraints they face in output maximization.

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted in Imo State, Nigeria. Imo State is located in the eastern part of Nigeria. The state lies between latitudes 4°45'N and 7°15'N and longitudes 6°50'E and 7°25'E [(Nigerian Meteorological Agency (NiMET), 2020)]. It is bounded to the east by Abia State, to the west by the River Niger and Delta State, and to the north by Anambra State, while Rivers State lies to the south (NBC, 2020). Imo State covers an area of 5,067.20 km², with a population of 3,934,899 persons (National Population Commission (NPC), 2006; National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), 2007) and population density of 725km² (Ministry of Land Survey and Urban Planning, 2015). The state has three agricultural zones: Okigwe, Orlu, and Owerri. These divisions are for administrative and extension services and not for any agro-ecological difference. It is also delineated into 27 Local Government Areas (LGAs). It has an average annual temperature of 28°C, an average annual relative humidity of 80%, an average annual rainfall of 1800–2500 mm, and an altitude of 100m above sea level [(National Root Crops Research Institute, Umudike Meteorological Station, (NRCRIMS), 2020)]. The state experiences two major seasons: dry and rainy. It has fertile and well-drained soil suitable for cassava farming, and a good proportion of the population is essentially cassava farmers. Other crops cultivated in the area include; vegetable, melon, yam. All of this necessitated the selection of the study area. The study sample was drawn from cassava farmers in the study area. Multi-stage and purposive sampling procedures were used to select the study respondents. A purposive sampling procedure was used to select farmers who were members of various cassava production groups. A sampling frame (with a population of 546 farmers) containing the current list of cassava farmers was obtained from the offices of the Nigeria Cassava Growers Association (NCGA); Imo Agricultural Development Program (Imo-ADP); and Nigeria Incentive-Based Risk Sharing System for Agricultural Lending (NIRSAL) in the state. The lists were merged to obtain the aggregate sample size from the sample framing. First, the three (3) agricultural zones of the state (Okigwe, Orlu, and Owerri) were randomly selected for the study. Second, four (4) Local Government Areas (LGAs) were purposively selected from each of the three (3) agricultural zones due to the presence of output-oriented farmers from the merged lists to give a total of 12 LGAs for the study. Subsequently, four (4) communities were randomly selected from each of the

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twelve (12) selected LGAs which gave a total of 48 communities for the study. Furthermore, two (2) villages were selected from each of the 48 communities to give a total of ninety-six (96) villages. Finally, two (2) farmers were selected from each of the ninety-six (96) villages to give a total sample size (n) of one-hundred and ninety-two (192) cassava farmers for the study. Primary data were used for study. The data were collected using structured questionnaire and supported with an oral interview in places where the respondents could neither read nor write. The questionnaire was carefully prepared based on the study objectives. The questionnaire contained both open-ended and closed-ended questions. Similarly, the questionnaire was subjected to content validity with the help of the research supervisors before being administered to the respondents. The data that were collected for the study includes the socio-economic characteristics of the cassava farmers, the cassava farmers' output maximization, and the constraints that cassava farmers face toward output maximization in the area. The data used for the study were cross-sectional and were collected from January 2023 to January 2025. Enumerators were engaged and trained for data collection, collation, coding, cleaning, and entry. Furthermore, in estimating the output maximization of the cassava farmers the Cobb-Douglas Production Function (CDPF) was used. The implicit model for the CDPF equation to be used was given as follows:

$$\ln Y_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln X_1 + \beta_2 \ln X_2 + \beta_3 \ln X_3 + \beta_4 \ln X_4 + \beta_5 \ln X_5 + \beta_6 \ln X_6 + (V_i - U_i) \dots \dots (1.0)$$

Where:

$\ln Y$ = Output (kg)

β_0 = Constant

$\beta_1 - \beta_7$ = Estimated regression coefficients

X_1 = Farm size (ha)

X_2 = Labour (man-days)

X_3 = Quantity of cassava stem cuttings (₦)

X_4 = Fertilizer (kg)

X_5 = Equipment (₦)

X_6 = Rents on Farmland (₦)

\ln = logarithm to base-e

ij = j^{th} observation of the i^{th} farmer

V_i = is a two-sided, normally distributed stochastic random error term

While Output Maximization (OM) effect U_i was given as:

$$OM \square U_i \sigma_u^2 + \sigma_v^2 + \sum o^2 + \sigma_v^2 \square_k Z_k \dots \dots \dots (2.0)$$

Where: Z_k = Socio-economic variables that influenced OM, and included variables are stated below;

Z_1 = Education (years)

Z_2 = Membership of cooperative (Member = 1, Non-member = 0)

Z_3 = Extension contact (Contact = 1, no-contact = 0)

Z_4 = Household size (number of persons in the households),

Z_5 = Farming experience (years)

\square_k = Unknown parameters.

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The unknown parameters of the model, namely the β and δ coefficients, as well as the composite variance parameter ($\sigma^2 = \sigma_u^2 + \sigma_v^2$), were estimated simultaneously. The parameter γ , defined as $\gamma = \sigma_u^2 / (\sigma_u^2 + \sigma_v^2)$, measures the proportion of the total variance attributable to the inefficiency component (u_i). Thus, the value of γ indicates the relative contribution of the variance associated with the distribution of the OM influence (u_i) to the overall disturbance term.

Table 1: Sampling and sample proportion for the Okigwe Agricultural Zone of Imo State

Imo Agricultural Zones	Selected Government Areas	Local Communities	Names and Number of Selected Villages		Two (2) farmers were randomly selected from each of the four (4) villages to give a total of eight (8) farmers; Sample size (n) Stage 5	
			Stage 3	Stage 4		
Okigwe	Okigwe	Ikigwu	Umuka	Umuokpara	8	8
		Otanzu	Amaeze-Ogii	Umuawa-Ogee		
		Umulolo	Agbobu	Agbuala		
		Ihube	Agbala	Akpugo		
	Onuimo	Okwe	Owerre	Umucheke	8	8
		Okwelle	Umuduruebo	Umuoma		
		Umuduru-Egbeaguru	Okohia	Ofiahia		
		Umuna	Uhi	Diakoma		
	Ehime-Mbano	Umueze-I	Umuihim	Umuodu	8	8
		Nsu	Ikpe	Ihitte		
		Umuezeala	Umuopara	Umuezeal-ama		
		Umunumo	Umuchima	Eze/obom		
	Ihitte/Uboma	Amakohia	Amuzu	Ipinweke	8	8
		Umuezegwu	Umuakpi	Umudibia		
		Ato-werem	Umuezina	Elugwu		
		Umuihi	Ikenafo	Uhegbu		
Total	4 LGAs	16 Communities	16 Villages	16 Villages	32	32
Sub-total		16 Communities	32 Villages		64	Cassava farmers

Source: Field Survey Data, 2025

Table 2: Sampling and sample proportion for the Orlu Agricultural Zone of Imo State

Imo Agricultural Zones	Selected Government Areas	Local Names and Number of Selected Communities	Names and Number of Selected Villages		Two (2) farmer were randomly selected from each of the four (4) villages to give a total of eight (8) farmers; Sample size (n) Stage 5	
Stage 1	Stage 2	Stage 3	Stage 4			
Orlu	Orlu	Amaifeke	Amadim	Ihunachi	8	8
		Umuna	Ebenator	Amoji		
		Ihitte-Owerre	Amanator	Obinugwu		
		Umudioka	Umudim	Umudiokauka		
	Ideato-North	Osina	Eluama	Ofe-eke	8	8
		Akokwa	Umuokegwu	Owerre-Akokwa		
		Urualla	Amaokwu	Ezemazi		
		Uzill	Ezihi	Umuonuoha		
	Ideato-South	Dikenafai	Umufai	Umueju	8	8
		Ntueke	Okorobi	Umueze		
		Ubiohia	Agballa	Okwu		
		Umuchima	Uhala	Okoroduruaku		
	Orsu	Asa-Uberielem	Umuidi	Umucheke	8	8
		Awo-idemili	Amadim	Obibi		
		Eziama	Urualla	Amakpara		
		Orsu-ihitteUkwu	Etiti	Uda		
Total	4 LGAs	16 Communities	16 Villages	16 Villages	32	32
Sub-total		16 Communities	32 Villages		64	Cassava farmers

Source: Field Survey Data, 2025

Table 3: Sampling and sample proportion for the Owerri Agricultural Zone of Imo State

Imo Agricultural Zones	Selected Local Government Areas	Names and Number of Selected Communities	Names and Number of Selected Villages		Two (2) farmers were randomly selected from each of the four (4) villages to give a total of eight (8) farmers; Sample size (n)	
Stage 1	Stage 2	Stage 3	Stage 4		Stage 5	
Owerri	Owerri North	Ihitte-Ogada	Amakohia	Akwakuma	8	8
		Naze	Umueri	Umuakali		
		Emii	Emeoha	Ezuala		
		Emekuku	Akalovo	Awaka		
	Ngor-okpala	Eziama	Amaedo	Egbelu	8	8
		Ntu	Umuokporntu	Umuaka-ntu		
		Obike	Amaedo	Amandara		
		Elelem	Mbutu	Oda		
	Ikeduru	Akabo	Abazu	Umuohia	8	8
		Amaimo	Amuzu	Umueze		
		Amakohia	Amaoba	Ogwu		
		Eziama-Ikeduru	Amachi	Ogada		
	Oguta	Awa	Akabor	Abiaziam	8	8
		Eguoma	Amagu	Omadi		
		Egwe	Ihitte-egwu	Eziama		
		Mgbelle	Ndiabiara	Uba		
Total	4 LGAs	16 Communities	16 Villages	16 Villages	32	32
Sub-total		16 Communities	32 Villages		64 Cassava farmers	
			Aggregate sample size (n): 64 +64+64		192 Cassava farmers	

Source: Field Survey Data, 2025

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Socioeconomic Characteristics of Cassava Farmers

Table 3 presents the results of the cassava farmers' distribution based on socio-economic characteristics.

Table 3: Distribution of the socioeconomic characteristics of the farmers

S/No	Socio-economic Characteristics	Mean (\bar{x})/Percentage (%)
1	Age (years)	43 years
2	Sex (male percentage)	0.63
3	Marital status (percentage of married farmers)	0.73
4	Household size (number of households)	8.00
5	Education (years spent in school)	Twelve years (equivalent to secondary education)
6	Farming experience (years)	25
7	Cooperative membership (percentage of members)	100.0
8	Annual farm income (Naira)	₦740,000.00 (\$546.63).
9	Farm size (measured in hectares)	1.80 (27 plots)
10	Access to farm credit (percentage of access to farm credit)	100.0
11	Extension contact (percentage of contact)	0.80
12	Annual output of cassava farmers (kg)	20,600

Source: Field Survey Data, 2025

Table 3 shows that the mean age was 43.00years. This implies that farmers are still in their middle age and are expected to be active and, full of strength and energy to face the stress and strain involved in cassava production output maximization in the area. Farmers within this age (41-50 years), are able to practice several modern output maximization strategies to increase their yield, income, and standard of living in the area. This agrees with the findings of Mohidem et al. (2022), who reported that the majority of farmers in Nigeria are within the age range of 41-50 and are in their innovative productive age, and possess the physical and mental energy required for cassava production compared with older farmers who are always not enthusiastic about modern farm economics, especially if the benefits are not expected in the near future. The results also indicate that a greater proportion (63.00%) of the farmers were males. This finding implies that both sexes are involved in the output maximization of cassava production, but males were more abundant in the area. The probable reasons for the high number of males could be because of their easier access to agricultural productive resources, such as farmland, labor, agricultural extension services, and farm credit than females in the area. This result agrees with the findings of Ibrahim et al. (2025), who asserted that men usually make most household farming decisions and

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have greater control over farm productive resources. This could also be because male farmers have more physical energy than female farmers to withstand the stress and strain involved in cassava crop output maximization. This finding is consistent with the result of Esiobu et al. (2024), who reported that males constituted the greater proportion of those involved in farming activities in southeast Nigeria. Table 3 shows that, greater proportions (73.96%) of the farmers were married. The study implies that cassava farmers in the area were more married individuals. Married individuals are viewed as responsible according to societal standards. The responsibility implies that they have access to productive resources, which could enable them to apply the best production method to achieve sustainable output maximization in the area. This finding supports the work of Kundiri et al. (2022), who opined that married individuals tend to have easy access to productive farm resources, combined production capital, ideas, and information to enhance their output, income, and standard of living. This result is also consistent with the findings of Wilcox et al. (2022), who found that married farmers are most likely to have easy access to productive farm resources such as land, large households, and pooled financial resources to increase their production. The mean household size was 8.0 persons. This implies that the cassava farmers have a relatively high household size, which is expected to promote farm labor supply for improving cassava output maximization in the area. Higher household size promotes the availability of labor. The result is in consonance with the study of Esiobu (2019), who found that farmers with a sizeable number of households have the potential to have increased access to farm labor, farm expansion, information sharing, and pooled financial resources for improving yield, income, and standard of living. Table 3 shows that the average year of formal education was 12 years. Education would be vital in positively influencing the kind of modern measures farmers would practice in increasing cassava production output maximization. This finding is consistent with the result of Mpombo et al. (2022), who asserted that higher education positively influences farmers' decision-making and understanding of output maximization to significantly increase yield, income, and standard of living. Similarly, the mean number of years of experience in farming was 25.00 years. This is an indication that farmers were quite experienced in cassava production and may have been practicing several output maximization strategies to significantly increase yield, income, and standard of living. This result is strengthened by the findings of Omoikhoje and Bigirimana (2022), who reported that farmers' level of experience in the production of a particular commodity is one of the key determinants of their ability to maximize output and income given available inputs. The finding is also in agreement with the result of Falola et al. (2022), who asserted that agribusiness experience promotes farmers' decision to practice better, more efficient, and more sustainable farm production strategies to increase yield, income, and standard of living. The majority (80.00%) of the cassava farmers had contact with extension agents. All the cassava farmers (100.0%) were members of cooperatives in the area. This could be because the study selected farmers from various cassava groups in the area. Therefore, they already understand the importance of a cooperative society within various groups in the area. In addition, most government interventions for farmers on cassava crops are accessed through strengthened cooperative societies. For cassava farmers in the area, cooperative membership is not only considered a useful mechanism for them to significantly improve their output maximization but also to manage risks for members, share information and labor, and pool, their limited resources together to improve income and socioeconomic activities. The finding is supported by the result of Donkor et al. (2022), who argued

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that in the output environment, involvement in cooperative society is one of the major determinants necessary for farmers to participate in the output market, as it gives farmers the opportunity to increase their output, sell their produce with maximum profit, and obtain relevant information on price trends and market conditions. In addition, the mean annual farm income in the 2023/2024 farming season was ₦740,000.00 (\$546.63), which gives an average monthly farm income was ₦70,000 (\$51.64). This is relatively higher and exactly the Nigeria Monthly [National Minimum wage of ₦70,000.00 [(National Salaries, Incomes and Wages Commission (NSIWC, 2024)]. This income could be attributed to farmers' output maximization potentials. The study demonstrates that farmers are members of a strengthened cooperative society that affords them access to credit, information, pooled labor, modern innovation, and the market. Therefore, farmers are expected to have a reasonable farm income. Cassava is one of the demand-driven and food security crops because of its various forms of usage (Igbaifua et al., 2022). Hence, farmers who produce large on quantities and based on consumer needs and wants, are expected to have a reasonable farm income over time. Higher-income-earning farmers may be less risk averse, understand how to address challenges of output maximization, and have more access to relevant information and farm expansion. This result is in parity with the findings of Orgu et al. (2024), who reported that farmers with higher farm income make better decisions, have access to necessary productive inputs, realize huge yield/output, and are more likely to be output-oriented in production than their counterparts who have low farm income. More so, all the cassava farmers (100.0%) access to credit. This could be because all the farmers were members of cooperative societies in the area and were drawn from various cassava farmers associations. This is a positive sign for farmers in terms of maximizing their output strategies in the area. Cassava crop is crucial in food security and requires inputs for its production. Therefore, farmers without access to credit are unlikely to maximize output and increase their income and standard, of living. Agricultural credit one of the most essential instruments for improving and sustaining agricultural production, and farmers are always in need of such instruments (i.e., credits) because of the seasonal pattern of their activities and the uncertainty they face (Esiobu et al., 2023). This is an indication that most farmers have contact with extension agents, which is expected to improve their technical skills and knowledge in increasing the area's output maximization strategies. Close and regular contact with the farmers is essential. The extension agent transmits problem-solving information to farmers and challenges to farmers back to the research institute. Close and regular contact with the farmers is essential. Extension agents transmit problem-solving information to farmers, and farmers' challenges are transmitted back to the research institute. This study is consistent with Oziokoi et al. (2022), who asserted that extension contact enhances farmers' information and knowledge on modern farm techniques to increase their output, income, and standard of living. Table 3 shows that the mean farm size was 1.80 hectares. The farmers have a relatively small farm size, which indicates that they are smallholder farmers operating on a farm size of less than 2.00 hectares. This small farm size could also be attributed to the increasingly predominant system of land tenure and urbanization the area. Small farmland could significantly affect the capacity of farmers for output maximization in the area. Farmers with larger farms are likely to practice more and better production strategies to maximize output. Larger farms often have access to economies of scale, meaning that the average cost of production decreases as the farm size increases. This is due to the ability to spread fixed costs (such as machinery, infrastructure, and management) over a larger output. Larger

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farms can achieve higher levels of efficiency and cost-effectiveness. The findings of this study are consistent with those of Baba et al. (2022), who found that a large farm size increases farmers' production capacity, output, and potential to scale-up production at all times. The average annual output was 20,600 kg, which is equivalent to 20.60 tons per year. This is relatively higher, which indicates that there could be a surplus for sale but May still not meet the increasing market demand for cassava tuber. It is also an indication that the cassava crop has a yield per hectare with adequate management practices given the available productive resources. Esiobu (2024), asserted that output-oriented agricultural production has the potential to increase farmers' output, income, and standard of living given the optimal use of available productive inputs.

3.2 Determinants of the Cassava Farmers' Output Maximization (OM) Potentials

Results of output maximization of the cassava farmers using cobb-douglas production function are presented in Table 4. Findings revealed that most of the parameters (farm size, quantity of cassava cuttings, and fertilizer) had a positive and significant coefficient with output maximization in the production function, whereas that of labor (β_3) and equipment (β_5). The three significant and positive variables were farm size (β_1), quantity of cassava stem cuttings (β_2) and fertilizer (β_4) which were all statistically significant at the 1% level of probability. This indicates that if the farm size and quantity of cassava stem cuttings are increased by 1%, the output of cassava crop would be maximized by 37.20% and 21.50%, respectively. Moreover, if fertilizer application increases by 1%, cassava yield would increase by 10.40%. Furthermore, the coefficient of labor (β_3) (-0.031) and equipment (β_5) (-0.053) were negative. This implies that an increase in labor and equipment by 1% decreases total output by 3.1% and 5.3%, respectively. This is true because the more labor employed on the same farm size, it would lead to over use of labor or excess labor which in turn leads to a reduction in output and income. This corroborates the study of Ludmila et al. (2022), who found that the overuse of farm labor increases production costs and decreases output. In addition, to maximize output, farmers may need to consider increasing the quality of cassava stem, farm size, and fertilizers. The estimated sigma square (σ^2) of 758.96 was statistically significant at the 1% level of probability and hence assures the goodness of fit and correctness of the composite error distributional assumptions. The estimated gamma parameter (Γ) was 0.942, indicating that 94.20% of the total variation in the output maximized of the cassava farmers was due to the relationship between the input and output use, and the remaining 5.80% was accounted for in the stochastic error. This also indicates that the unexplained variations in output maximization are the major sources of random errors. It also confirms the presence of the one-sided error component in the model; hence, the use of the OLS in estimating the function becomes, inadequate in representing the data. The total sum of elasticities of the Cobb-Douglas production model gives the returns to scale (RtS) of 0.622, indicating that farmers were maximizing output at Stage II of the production region; hence, resources and output were moderately maximized at this stage. Esiobu (2019), Fan et al. (2022), and Carlos and Liesbeth (2022), asserted that Stage, II of the production region is one of the most rational stages to maximize output. This is because in Stage I, the maximization of output tends to increase at an increasing rate, which means that farmers tend to maximize the total output at an increasing rate. This is an indication that farmers were producing for market sales, but they may not have reached their production potentials. There is still room for improvement. When farmers are able to adequately maximize output from a given quantity of inputs, surplus for market sales, increased income, and and improved standard

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of living would result..The generalized likelihood test gave a value -936.69 which indicates that farmers are not adequately maximizing output from a given quantity of inputs. The findings of this study are consistent with those of Ezike et al. (2022) and Ajiferuke (2022), who suggested that increasing farmers’ socioeconomic standard, access to productive inputs, and strengthened extension services are among the efforts that should be made to enhance the current scope of cassava production in Nigeria. Similarly, the result of the stochastic frontier cost function in Table 4 reveals that all the independent variables gave a positive coefficient. The result implies that as these factors increase, the cost increases while the total output maximized increases. The significant variables were farmland depreciation, cost of quality of cassava cuttings, and output, all of which were statistically significant at the 1% level of probability. The gamma (γ) estimate was 0.930 and was significant at the 1% level, indicating that 93.00% of the variations in output maximized were caused by the differences in the use of inputs. The sigma square (δ^2) was 4.852 and was significant at the 1% probability level, indicating the goodness of fit and correctness of the specified assumptions of the stochastic error term distribution. The generalized likelihood test gave a value of -4845.048 which indicate that the farmers did not adequately maximize output. However, there is ample opportunity for significant improvement in the cassava farmers’ output maximization in the study area. Otegunrin et al. (2022) and Sanusi et al. (2022), reported that adequate training/orientation of farmers toward output maximization, productive inputs, improved technologies, and other modern farming practices have significant potential for maximizing output, sales, and income.

Table 4: Determinants of the Cassava Farmers’ Output Maximization (OM) Potentials

Variables of production function	Parameters	Coefficient	t-value	Cost-function variables	Parameters	Coefficient	t-value
Constant	β_0	62.853	8.953** *	Constant	β_0	-595.830	- 10.842** *
Farm size	β_1	0.330	5.092** *	Rents on farmland	β_1	0.523	3.512***
Quantity of cassava stem cut	β_2	0.237	4.575** *	Cost of quantity of cassava cutting	β_2	1.531	6.201***
Labor	β_3	-0.022	-0.059	Cost of labor	β_3	0.067	-0.362
Fertilizer	β_4	0.104	6.953** *	Cost of fertilizer	β_4	0.421	0.064
Farm equipment’s	β_5	-0.027	-0.082	Cost of farm equipment’s	β_5	0.246	0.025
OM Explanatory				Output	Y	492.532	6.558**

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Variables							
Education	Z ₁	0.520	5.057** *	Sigma-square	σ ²	652.854	4.852***
Membership of cooperative	Z ₂	0.306	4.320** *	Gamma	Γ	0.930	5.973***
Extension contact	Z ₃	0.652	5.321** *	Log -likelihood function	L(θ)	- 4845.048	
Household size	Z ₄	0.259	4.962** *				
Farming experience	Z ₅	0.430	4.425** *				
Sigma-square	σ ²	758.96	5.963** *				
Gamma	Γ	0.942	13.592* **				
Log -likelihood function	L(θ)	-936.69					
Return to the Scale	(RtS)	0.622					
Sample size	N	192					

OM: Output Maximization; *statistically significant at 10%; **statistically significant at 5%; *statistically significant at 1%; Source: Frontier 4.1 (2025)**

On the other hand, from the explanatory variables influencing OM, educational level had a positive coefficient with OM of cassava farmers; hence, it was statistically significant at the 1% level of probability. This implies that an increase in the number of years of formal education leads to an increase in the quantity of output maximized from a given input. Thus, farmers with higher education years are in a better position to be more oriented toward output maximization than their counterparts with no or less education. Farmers with higher levels of education likely respond positively to the use of improved technology, such as the application of fertilizers, use of improved cassava breed, use of pesticides, and herbicides, among others, thus enabling the farmers to produce close to the output maximization frontier. This agrees with the findings of Tafesse et al. (2021) and Dizyee et al. (2022). Education increases the ability to perceive, interpret, and react to new ideas and improves farmers' managerial skills (Olanrewaju et al., 2022). This finding also supports the study of Wilcox et al. (2022), who opined that a higher level of education determines the quality of farmers' managerial skills, their thinking abilities, and how well informed they are about the innovations and technologies around them. Membership in a cooperative had a positive coefficient with cassava farmers' output maximization, and it was statistically significant at the 1% level of probability. This implies that cassava farmers who are members of cooperative societies gather more information, share ideas, exchange labor, and acquire a reasonable amount of credit and knowledge on how to maximize output and surplus for the market. Cooperative membership affords

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farmers easy access to farm credit, information, ideas, and collective demand (Omoikhoje & Bigirimana, 2022). Similarly, Donkor et al. (2022), found that cooperative membership was positive and significantly related to farmers' surplus and marketable output. Extension contact was positively related to the cassava farmers' output maximization. This indicates that a unit increase in extension contact leads to a significant increase in cassava farmers' output maximization. Farmers who receive more visits and/or are in frequent contact with extension agents are in a better position to maximize their output and have a surplus for household consumption and the market. The relationship was significant at a probability level of 1%. Ozioko et al. (2022) argued that extension contact enhances farmers' production and promotes their knowledge of modern farming methods. Bandumula et al. (2022) showed that extension contact was positive and significantly related to cassava farmers' output. Household size had a significant and positive coefficient with cassava farmers' output maximization. This implies that farmers with larger households maximized their output more than their counterparts with smaller households. The effect of household size on farm-level cassava production is traceable to its use as a source of labor supply for farm work, thereby increase in maximizing output. This relationship was significant at the probability level of 1%. This finding supports the result of Ariel and Hochkofler (2022), who reported that large household size is a proxy for labor availability, cost reduction of hired labor and expansion of farm size. Farming experience had a positive coefficient with cassava farmers' output maximization; hence, it was statistically significant at the 1% level of probability. This implies that a year increase in farming experience leads to a significant increase in cassava farmers' output maximization. This indicates that the more experienced cassava farmers understand the problems involved in output maximization, the better positioned they are to overcome them. This finding is in parity with the study of Mwebaze et al. (2022) and Esiobu (2023), who reported that farmers with more years of farming experience would be more output oriented in production, have better knowledge of climatic conditions, and market situation and are thus expected to run a profitable enterprise.

3.3 Cassava farmers' constraints in output maximization

Findings of the cassava farmer distributions based on their constraints in output maximization are shown in Figure 1. The results show that inadequate production capital (98.96%) and limited availability of farmland (96.88%) were identified by the farmers as among the constraints they face in the use of cassava output maximization in the area. This could be attributed to the high cost of the production inputs. Inadequate production capital hinders farmers from obtaining the necessary resources and technologies to maximize output and remain in production over time. This constraint makes most farmers unable to adequately maximize output for market sales, increase income, and attain large-scale production. Esiobu (2019), reported similar results in Nigeria regarding the constraints facing farmers in cassava production. Similarly, the limited availability of farmland (96.88%) may be attributed to the land tenure system or the increasing population the area. It was earlier found in the study that a unit increase in farm size results in an, increase in the cassava farmers' output. The implication of the findings is that farmers might have several quantities of cassava to cultivate or modern production methods to practice to maximize output, but limited farm size would continue to compel them to intensively farm on a small plot of land, hence unable to attained adequate output maximization. Also, being output-oriented implies that farmers must produce and maximize output adequately to meet market demand,

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however, when farmers have limited farmland, achieving it becomes difficult, if not impossible. Osuagwu et al. (2025) reported that the limited availability of farmland is one of the major factors limiting agricultural production across Nigeria. On the other hand, poor storage and processing facilities (87.00%), poor market infrastructures (72.00%), long distance between farms and market (51.00%), and high cost of labor (44.00%) were stated by the farmers as the constraints they face in cassava output maximization in the area. Poor storage and processing facilities left most farmers unable to process and store their produce for future sales. Cassava produce can be added to various values; however, in the absence of good storage and processing facilities, it becomes difficult, thereby reducing farmers' income. Farmers may be compelled to sell their cassava produce at a lower price due to lack of storage facilities and fear of spoilage. Several studies, such as Esiobu (2016), Otekunrin et al. (2022), and Igbaifua et al. (2022), have confirmed that poor storage and processing facilities are some of the major problems of market orientation in Nigeria. The long distance between farms and the market left most farmers to sell at the farm gate at a reduced price. Farmers are often compelled, if not forced, to sell their produce at a very low price to avoid huge wastage or total loss. The long distance between farms and markets makes most farmers resort to farm gate sales after harvest, thereby losing a greater proportion of their produce to exploitative and dubious middlemen in the area. Esiobu and Onubuogu (2014) and Merem et al. (2022) stated that efficient road networks are required to move products from where they are produced to where they are consumed or sold. The majority of rural roads in the study area is in deplorable conditions and requires good roads to ensure effective distribution of agricultural produce. Market infrastructure, access to market information, and price fluctuation are also affected... Furthermore, the farmers identified high cost of labor, high cost of production input, and poor extension contact as among the constraints they face in using market-orientation strategies in the area. Osuagwu et al. (2022), asserted that the high cost of inputs and farm labor are some of the major challenges faced by most African farmers. Poor contact with extension agents left most of the farmers unable to obtain the right information on planting methods and how to purchase improved cassava stem cuttings to maximize output and market sales. Planting poor-breed cassava stem cuttings is tantamount to a waste of effort because such stem cuttings are more prone to infection with pests and diseases than good cassava stem cuttings. A poor cassava stem cutting breed makes farms' investment less profitable if not a complete loss and reduces farmers' output maximization and market sales (Falola et al., 2022). Ultimately, there is no doubt that these constraints are responsible for the farmers' inability to optimally maximize cassava production in the area. Confronting these constraints with multiple sustainable remedies would be vital in adequately enhancing not only the output maximization of cassava production but also the income and farmers' standard of living in the area.

Figure 1: Cassava farmers' constraints in output maximization

3.5 Conclusion

In conclusion, this study assessed the determinants of output maximization among cassava farmers in Imo State, Nigeria, using the Cobb-Douglas Production Function and descriptive statistics. Cassava farming in the area is dominated by middle-aged, experienced male farmers with moderate educational backgrounds, relatively large household sizes, widespread cooperative membership, and access to credit and extension services. The average annual cassava output of 20,600kg and a returns-to-scale (RtS) of 0.622 indicate that farmers are operating in Stage II of the production region, indicating that they are moderately maximizing output but not yet at optimal efficiency. Key factors that positively influence output maximization include farm size, cassava cutting quantity, fertilizer use, education level, cooperative membership, extension contact, household size, and farming experience. The major constraints to output maximization include limited production capital and farmland availability. The stochastic frontier analysis further confirmed that while cassava farmers are performing moderately well, there is still significant potential for targeted interventions to improve output efficiency.

3.6 Recommendations

The following recommendations are made based on the study's major findings.

- i. To boost productivity, government and development partners should subsidize and improve access to inputs such as improved cassava stem varieties, fertilizers, and mechanization tools.

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- ii. Cassava farmers should be encouraged and supported to operate through strengthened cooperatives that can serve as platforms for collective bargaining, access to finance, training, and market linkages.
 - iii. State and local governments should explore strategies to expand farmland availability through land reforms or leasing schemes that facilitate access for smallholder farmers.
 - iv. Extension agents should increase contact frequency with farmers to disseminate knowledge on modern farming techniques and cassava production-specific output-maximization strategies.
 - v. Agricultural training programs targeting cassava producers should be implemented to improve farm management practices, financial planning, and technological adoption.
 - vi. Existing agricultural credit schemes should be scaled up, with simplified loan procedures tailored to smallholder needs to ensure, that farmers can access the capital needed for input procurement and expansion.
 - vii. Stakeholders should invest in developing robust cassava value chains and market infrastructure to ensure that farmers have guaranteed off-take and pricing incentives for scaling production.
- Significant improvements in output maximization can be achieved by addressing the outlined constraints and leveraging the strengths of the cassava farming cooperative society, leading to increased income, food security, and economic resilience in Imo State and beyond.

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Conflicts of Interest

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